

Inverse Method for Order n Matrix

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Abstract

The power of matrix algebra was seen not only in applied mathematics, applied sciences, engineering but also in economics, sociology, modern psychology and industrial management (i.e., system of linear equation, cryptography, optics, signal processing, image processing, graph theory, Machine Learning, Data Science etc.). In practice the matrix inverse methods is suitable only for non-singular small system because the higher the size of the system the more difficult finding the inverse of the system even with the help of software/application. With experience we were able to find the inverse of order 4, 5, ... , n matrix with ease and also verified the method by computing $AA^{-1} = I$.

Keywords: Matrix; Determinant; Inverse Method; Cryptography; Data Science

1. Introduction

Matrix (Plural matrices) is a Square or rectangular array of an elements (which are usually numbers) in rows and columns.

The general form of matrix with m rows and n column is:

$$A = \begin{bmatrix} a_{11} & a_{21} & \cdot & \cdot & \cdot & a_{1n} \\ a_{12} & a_{22} & \cdot & \cdot & \cdot & a_{2n} \\ \cdot & \cdot & \cdot & \cdot & \cdot & \cdot \\ \cdot & \cdot & \cdot & \cdot & \cdot & \cdot \\ a_{m1} & a_{m2} & \cdot & \cdot & \cdot & a_{mn} \end{bmatrix}$$

Which is written in compact form as $A_{mn} = [a_{ij}]_{mn}$

1.1. Statement of the Problem

In practice the matrix inverse methods is suitable only for non-singular small system (2 by 2 and 3 by 3 matrix). Hence, the need for order 4, 5, 6, ... , n matrix.

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1.2. Aim and Objectives of the Study

This research paper aim to solve inverse of 4 by 4, 5 by 5, ... , n by n non-singular matrix.

1.2.1. The specific objectives are to

- find the determinant of n by n matrix
- test for non-singularity of the matrix if singular stop else
- find $Adjoint(A) = [A_{ij}]^T$
- Compute $A^{-1} = \frac{1}{\det(A)} \times Adjoint(A)$.
- Verified by computing $AA^{-1} = I$.

1.3. Scope and Limitation

The study is restricted in finding inverse of order 4, 5, ... , n non-singular matrix.

1.4. Significance of the Study

The field of matrix is fortunate to be blessed with lots of contribution but scholars used to restrict themselves on 3 by 3 matrix when it comes to matrix inverse method. As an optimizers we dimmed it fit to teach our student how to obtain inverse of order n because we do believe that unravelling the full strength of any method will certainly help our young one to think more deeply and be able to develop more sophisticated devices, applications etc. in time to come [1].

1.5. Operational Definition of Basic Terms

1.5.1. Transpose is an operator that flips a matrix over its diagonal

1.5.2. Sign factor is a + (plus) or - (minus) sign that is attached to each entry element of a matrix (i.e., if $(-1)^{i+j} = \text{even}$ then the sign factor for that element a_{ij} is + else it must be - (odd))

1.5.3 Minor (M_{ij}) is a determinant of some smaller square matrix generated from the original matrix (say A) by removing one or more of its rows and columns.

1.5.4 Cofactor (A_{ij}) it is calculated by multiplying the sign factor by the Minor

1.5.5 Adjoint matrix is the transpose of the cofactor matrix

1.5.6 Determinant is a scalar value computed for a given square matrix

2. History

Matrix concept has ancient roots, with some early ideas found in Chinese mathematics. Over the years, matrices have seen an extended use in research, social science, commerce and are being used in cryptography, computer graphics, economics, chemistry, optics geology, animation, communication, wireless, signal processing, robotics, image processing, machine learning, data science and finance. Matrices also have in particular a wide range of applications in science and have been applied to solve real-world problems. Matrices are used to represent real-world data, message encryption and decryption, cryptography, coding theory, creating 3-D image and 2-D motion, to compress electronic data and to store fingerprint data, robotics and automation, CT scans and MRI scans, in economics to calculate gross domestic products, wireless application protocol, profit prediction, UV spectroscopy, automobiles, etc. The matrices are used in physics while applying Kirchoff's Laws of Voltage and Current to solve problems, to explore electrical circuits, quantum mechanics and optics, to create graphs, calculate statistics, and conduct scientific research in a variety of domains. Matrices have a long history of use in solving linear equations, dating back to 300BC. [2, 3, 4, 5, 9, 10, 14].

2.1. Overview: Inverse Method

The square matrix A is called an invertible matrix if there exist a square matrix A^{-1} such that $AA^{-1} = I$ (where I is a unit matrix, provided that the two matrices are of the same order). Then A^{-1} is called an invertible matrix of A, denoted by A^{-1} .

It should be noted that, if A^{-1} is a square matrix and $\det. (A) \neq 0$ then A is an invertible matrix, and we always have the property $AA^{-1} = A^{-1}A = I$ and $A^{-1} = \frac{1}{\det(A)} \times Adj. (A)$ [6, 7, 8, 11, 13, 12, 15].

The divisibility of determinants within square matrices serves as a captivating area of study, offering profound insights into the underlying structures and properties of these mathematical constructs. By exploring the divisibility of determinants, researchers delve into the intricate interplay between the elements within matrices, unraveling patterns and relationships that underpin their mathematical behavior. This pursuit extends beyond mere theoretical conjecture, finding practical relevance in various fields where matrices are indispensable tools for problem-solving and analysis. Understanding the divisibility of determinants empowers professionals to optimize their use of matrices in diverse applications, enhancing their efficacy in tasks ranging from data analysis to algorithm design. Some significant advancements have been made regarding the divisibility among determinants of power matrices. Moreover, the study of the divisibility of determinants within square matrices represents a testament to the enduring relevance and versatility of mathematical concepts across different domains of knowledge. As scholars probe deeper into this phenomenon, they uncover connections that transcend disciplinary boundaries, shedding light on the underlying principles governing complex systems and phenomena.

An invertible matrix must be non-singular, meaning its determinant must be non-vanishing else the system is either linearly dependent or inconsistent. In Cryptography Matrix A is a key matrix which we used to encrypt our message and decrypt our messages by finding A^{-1} . Hence, one of the importance of learning how to find inverse of large systems. In optimization we often pay attention to details (i.e., see how we can come out with a result that is more accurate and more convergent than the existing/common knowledge) [1, 3, 7, 15].

3. Results

3.1. Linear Equation with two variables

Write the system of equation

$$2x + 3y = 4$$

$$5x + 4y = 17$$

In matrix form, find A^{-1} . Hence, solve the simultaneous linear equation

Solution

$$AX = B \quad (1)$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} 2 & 3 \\ 5 & 4 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} x \\ y \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 4 \\ 17 \end{bmatrix}$$

Table 1 Cofactor of order 2 matrix

(a_{ij}) th	a_{ij}	$(-1)^{i+j}$	M_{ij}	A_{ij}
a_{11}	2	+	4	4
a_{12}	3	-	5	-5
a_{21}	5	-	3	-3
a_{22}	4	+	2	2

$$|A| = \det. (A) = \sum_{j=1}^2 a_{1j} A_{1j} = a_{11}A_{11} + a_{12}A_{12} \quad (2)$$

$$= 2(4) + 3(-5)$$

$$= -7 \rightarrow \text{non-singular, hence matrix A is invertible}$$

$$A^{-1} = \frac{1}{|A|} \times \text{Adj.}(A) \quad (3)$$

$$\text{Adj.}(A) = (A_{ij})^T \quad (4)$$

$$\text{Adj.}(A) = \begin{bmatrix} 4 & -3 \\ -5 & 2 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$A^{-1} = \frac{1}{-7} \begin{bmatrix} 4 & -3 \\ -5 & 2 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$X = A^{-1}B \quad (5)$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} x \\ y \end{bmatrix} = \frac{1}{-7} \begin{bmatrix} 4 & -3 \\ -5 & 2 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} 4 \\ 17 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 5 \\ -2 \end{bmatrix}. \text{ Therefore, } (x, y) = (5, -2)$$

3.2. System of Linear Equation with three variables

Write the system of equation in matrix form, find A^{-1} , Hence, solve the simultaneous linear equation

$$x - y + 3z = 5$$

$$4x + 2y - z = 0$$

$$x + 3y + z = 5$$

Solution

$$AX = B$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} 1 & -1 & 3 \\ 4 & 2 & -1 \\ 1 & 3 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} x \\ y \\ z \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 5 \\ 0 \\ 5 \end{bmatrix}$$

Table 2 Cofactor of order 3 matrix

$(a_{ij})^{th}$	a_{ij}	$(-1)^{i+j}$	M_{ij}	A_{ij}
a_{11}	1	+	5	5
a_{12}	-1	-	5	-5
a_{13}	3	+	10	10
a_{21}	4	-	-10	10
a_{22}	2	+	-2	-2
a_{23}	-1	-	4	-4
a_{31}	1	+	-5	-5
a_{32}	3	-	-13	13
a_{33}	1	+	6	6

$$|A| = \det. (A) = \sum_{j=1}^3 a_{1j} A_{1j} = a_{11}A_{11} + a_{12}A_{12} + a_{13}A_{13} \quad (6)$$

$$= 1(5) + (-1)(-5) + 3(10)$$

= 40 → non-singular, hence matrix A is invertible

$$A^{-1} = \frac{1}{|A|} \times \text{Adj.}(A) \quad (7)$$

$$\text{Adj.}(A) = (A_{ij})^T \quad (8)$$

$$\text{Adj.}(A) = \begin{bmatrix} 5 & -5 & 10 \\ 10 & -2 & -4 \\ -5 & 13 & 6 \end{bmatrix}^T = \begin{bmatrix} 5 & 10 & -5 \\ -5 & -2 & 13 \\ 10 & -4 & 6 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$A^{-1} = \frac{1}{40} \begin{bmatrix} 5 & 10 & -5 \\ -5 & -2 & 13 \\ 10 & -4 & 6 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$X = A^{-1}B \quad (9)$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} x \\ y \\ z \end{bmatrix} = \frac{1}{40} \begin{bmatrix} 5 & 10 & -5 \\ -5 & -2 & 13 \\ 10 & -4 & 6 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} 5 \\ 0 \\ 5 \end{bmatrix} = \frac{1}{40} \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 40 \\ 80 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \\ 2 \end{bmatrix}.$$

Therefore, (x, y, z) = (0, 1, 2)

3.3. System of Linear Equation with four variables

Write the system

$$w + x + y - z = 2$$

$$4w + 4x + y + z = 0$$

$$w - x - y + 2z = 0$$

$$2w + x + 2y - 2z = 2$$

In matrix form, find A^{-1} . Hence, solve the simultaneous linear equation

Solution

$$AX = B$$

Table 3 Cofactor of order 4 matrix

$(a_{ij})^{th}$	a_{ij}	$(-1)^{i+j}$	M_{ij}	A_{ij}
a_{11}	1	+	-9	-9
a_{12}	1	-	2	--2
a_{13}	1	+	27	27
a_{14}	-1	-	-17	17
a_{21}	4	-	-1	1
a_{22}	4	+	0	0
a_{23}	1	-	3	-3
a_{24}	1	+	-2	-2
a_{31}	1	-	-2	-2

a_{32}	-1	-	0	0
a_{33}	-1	+	5	5
a_{34}	2	-	-3	3
a_{41}	2	-	-3	3
a_{42}	2	+	1	1
a_{43}	2	-	10	-10
a_{44}	-2	+	-6	-6

$$|A| = \det. (A) = \sum_{j=1}^4 a_{1j} A_{1j} = a_{11}A_{11} + a_{12}A_{12} + a_{13}A_{13} + a_{14}A_{14} \quad (10)$$

$$= 1(-9) + 1(-2) + 1(27) + (-1)17$$

= -1 → non-singular, hence matrix A is invertible

$$A^{-1} = \frac{1}{|A|} \times \text{Adj.}(A) \quad (11)$$

$$\text{Adj.}(A) = (A_{ij})^T \quad (12)$$

$$\text{Adj.}(A) = \begin{bmatrix} -9 & -2 & 27 & 17 \\ 1 & 0 & -3 & -2 \\ -2 & 0 & 5 & 3 \\ 2 & 1 & 2 & -6 \end{bmatrix}^T = \begin{bmatrix} -9 & 1 & -2 & 3 \\ -2 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 27 & -3 & 5 & -10 \\ 17 & -2 & 3 & -6 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$A^{-1} = \frac{1}{-1} \begin{bmatrix} -9 & 1 & -2 & 3 \\ -2 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 27 & -3 & 5 & -10 \\ 17 & -2 & 3 & -6 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$X = A^{-1}B \quad (13)$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} w \\ x \\ y \\ z \end{bmatrix} = \frac{1}{-1} \begin{bmatrix} -9 & 1 & -2 & 3 \\ -2 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 27 & -3 & 5 & -10 \\ 17 & -2 & 3 & -6 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} 2 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 2 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 12 \\ 2 \\ -34 \\ -22 \end{bmatrix}$$

Therefore, (w, x, y, z) = (12, 2, -34, -22)

3.4. System of Linear Equation with five variables

Write the system of equation

$$2v + 3w + x + y + 4z = 34$$

$$5v + 2w - 4x + 2y + z = 9$$

$$3v + w + 2x + 3y - 5z = -19$$

$$v + 2w + 3x + 4y + 7z = 53$$

$$4v - 3w + 2x - 5y + 2z = 37$$

In matrix form, find A^{-1} . Hence, solve the simultaneous linear equation

Solution

$$AX = B$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} 2 & 3 & 1 & 1 & 4 \\ 5 & 2 & -1 & 2 & 1 \\ 3 & 1 & 2 & 3 & -5 \\ 1 & 2 & 3 & 4 & 7 \\ 4 & -3 & 2 & -5 & 2 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} v \\ w \\ x \\ y \\ z \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 34 \\ 9 \\ -19 \\ 53 \\ 37 \end{bmatrix}$$

Table 4 Cofactor of order 5 matrix

$(a_{ij})_{th}$	a_{ij}	$(-1)^{i+j}$	M_{ij}	A_{ij}
a_{11}	2	+	150	150
a_{12}	3	-	1650	-1650
a_{13}	1	+	-516	-516
a_{14}	1	-	-954	954
a_{15}	4	+	126	126
a_{21}	5	-	546	-546
a_{22}	2	+	444	444
a_{23}	-1	-	-840	840
a_{24}	2	+	-432	-432
a_{25}	1	-	162	-162
a_{31}	3	+	-94	-94
a_{32}	1	-	202	-202
a_{33}	2	+	-616	-616
a_{34}	3	-	54	-54
a_{35}	-5	+	366	366
a_{41}	1	-	4	-4
a_{42}	2	+	662	662
a_{43}	3	-	184	-184
a_{44}	4	+	-594	-594
a_{45}	7	-	300	-300
a_{51}	4	+	-248	-248
a_{52}	-3	-	-256	256
a_{53}	2	+	-284	-284
a_{54}	-5	-	-252	252
a_{55}	2	+	-60	-60

$$|A| = \det. (A) = \sum_{j=1}^5 a_{1j} A_{1j} = a_{11}A_{11} + a_{12}A_{12} + a_{13}A_{13} + a_{14}A_{14} + a_{15}A_{15} \dots\dots\dots (15)$$

$$= 2(150) + 3 (-1650) + 1 (-516) + 1 (1954) + 4 (126)$$

= -3708 → non-singular, hence matrix A is invertible

$$A^{-1} = \frac{1}{|A|} \times \text{Adj.}(A) \quad (16)$$

$$\text{Adj.}(A) = (A_{ij})^T \quad (17)$$

$$\text{Adj.}(A) = \begin{bmatrix} 150 & -1650 & -516 & 954 & 126 \\ -546 & 444 & 840 & -432 & -162 \\ -94 & -202 & -616 & -54 & 360 \\ -4 & 662 & -184 & -594 & -300 \\ -248 & 256 & -284 & 252 & -60 \end{bmatrix}^T$$

$$X = A^{-1}B \quad (18)$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} v \\ w \\ x \\ y \\ z \end{bmatrix} = \frac{1}{-3708} \begin{bmatrix} 150 & -1650 & -516 & 954 & 126 \\ -546 & 444 & 840 & -432 & -162 \\ -94 & -202 & -616 & -54 & 360 \\ -4 & 662 & -184 & -594 & -300 \\ -248 & 256 & -284 & 252 & -60 \end{bmatrix}^T \begin{bmatrix} 34 \\ 9 \\ -19 \\ 53 \\ 37 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 2 \\ 1 \\ 5 \\ -2 \\ 6 \end{bmatrix}$$

Therefore, $(v, w, x, y, z) = (2, 1, 5, -2, 6)$

4. Discussion

Table 1, 2, 3 & 4 shows the a_{ij} entry elements of the given matrix, sign factor $(-1)^{i+j}$, minor (M_{ij}) and the respective cofactor (A_{ij}) . Equation 1 shows the standard form of writing simultaneous linear equation in matrix form. Equation 2, 6, 10 and 15 present the formula for computing determinant of order 2, 3, 4 and 5 matrix respectively. Equation 3, 7, 11 and 16 present the formula for computing A^{-1} of order 2, 3, 4 and 5 matrix respectively

Equation 4, 8, 12 and 17 present the formula for computing adjoint of order 2, 3, 4 and 5 matrix respectively. Equation 5, 9, 13 and 18 present the formula for computing unknowns of order 2, 3, 4 and 5 matrix respectively. It was proved that inverse method can be applied to non-singular matrix of higher order (i.e., 4, 5, ..., n).

5. Conclusion

Inverse method for solving order n non-singular matrix has been developed. Future research can consider implementing inverse method for solving order n matrix as software package and its deployment to different fields of knowledge.

Compliance with ethical standards

Disclosure of conflict of interest

No conflict of interest to be disclosed.

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